

Electronic Voting System Leveraging Blockchain

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DoI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15309419>

Abstract

E-Voting system using block chain works as a step towards creating secure and transparent environment for elections. Where the users will be able to cast their votes only once and will be able to view the total votes casted in real-time without having the permission to edit the same after elections get over. The working of block chains will ensure the votes are maintained and the systems are not rigged by any third party. The secure E-Voting system, uses block chain Which is a decentralized peer-to-peer transaction ledger. Every vote that is casted will be considered as an individual transaction. These votes will be counted and the results will then be announced. To limit the voting frauds and to make the voting and counting process very transparent, this system is required to convenient for the voters as well as this system minimize the cost for conducting the election, this is definitely cheaper method as compared to the current view of conducting election, Voting is a very important issue which can be beneficial in term of choosing the right leader in an election. A good leader can bring prosperity to a country and also can lead the country in the right direction every time. However, elections are surrounds with ballot forgery, coercion and multiple voting issues. Moreover, while giving votes, a person has to wait in a long queue and it is a very time-consuming process. In this paper, a fully decentralized e-voting system based on block chain technology is proposed. This protocol utilizes smart contract into the e-voting system to deal with security issues, accuracy and voters' privacy during the vote. The protocol results in a transparent, non-editable and independently verifiable procedure that discards all the intended fraudulent activities occurring